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THE IMPACT OF WTO MEMBERSHIP ON ATTRACTING FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT TO CHINA: LESSONS FOR UZBEKISTAN

ВЛИЯНИЕ ЧЛЕНСТВА В ВТО НА ПРИВЛЕЧЕНИЕ ПРЯМЫХ ИНОСТРАННЫХ ИНВЕСТИЦИЙ В КИТАЙ: УРОКИ ДЛЯ УЗБЕКИСТАНА

XITOYGA TO‘G‘RIDAN-TO‘G‘RI XORIJIY INVESTITSIYALARNI JALB ETISHDA JSTGA A‘ZOLIKNING TA‘SIRI: O‘ZBEKISTON UCHUN SABOQLAR

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Abstract. This article analyzes China’s accession to the World Trade Organization (WTO) and its impact on the volume of foreign direct investment (FDI). Based on statistical data from 1979 to 2023, the paper examines the dynamics of investment growth over this period. Drawing on China’s experience, the study provides recommendations for Uzbekistan in preparing for WTO membership, implementing institutional reforms, and improving the investment climate. As an alternative approach, strategic policy options tailored to Uzbekistan’s specific conditions are proposed, aiming to ensure investment stability and accelerate economic growth.

Keywords: WTO, FDI, investments, foreign trade, economic growth, trade system, global scale, international integration, development.

Аннотация. В статье анализируется вступление Китая во Всемирную торговую организацию (ВТО) и его влияние на объем прямых иностранных инвестиций (ПИИ). На основе статистических данных с 1979 по 2023 год в статье рассматривается динамика роста инвестиций за этот период. Опираясь на опыт Китая, в исследовании даются рекомендации для Узбекистана по подготовке к членству в ВТО, проведению институциональных реформ и улучшению инвестиционного климата. В качестве альтернативного подхода предлагаются варианты стратегической политики, адаптированные к конкретным условиям Узбекистана, направленные на обеспечение инвестиционной стабильности и ускорение экономического роста.

Ключевые слова: ВТО, ПИИ, инвестиции, внешняя торговля, экономический рост, торговая система, глобальный масштаб, международная интеграция, развитие.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada Xitoyning Jahon Savdo Tashkilotiga (JST) qo'shilishi va uning to'g'ridan-to'g'ri xorijiy investitsiyalar hajmiga ta'siri tahlil qilinadi. 1979 yildan 2023 yilgacha bo'lgan statistik ma'lumotlarga asoslanib, maqola ushbu davrdagi investitsiyalarning o'sish dinamikasini o'rganadi. Xitoy tajribasiga tayangan holda tadqiqot O'zbekistonga JSTga a'zolikka tayyorgarlik ko'rish, institutsional islohotlarni amalga oshirish va sarmoyaviy muhitni yaxshilash bo'yicha tavsiyalar beradi. Muqobil yondashuv sifatida investitsion barqarorlikni ta'minlash va iqtisodiy o'sishni jadallashtirishga qaratilgan O'zbekistonning o'ziga xos shartlariga moslashtirilgan strategik siyosat variantlari taklif etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: JST, TTXI, investitsiyalar, tashqi savdo, iqtisodiy o'sish, savdo tizimi, global miqyos, xalqaro integratsiya, rivojlanish.

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Introduction. In recent decades, the role of foreign direct investment (FDI) in the global economy has increased significantly. This trend has emerged as a crucial driver of economic growth, technological advancement, and international integration, particularly for developing countries. In this context, the accession of the People's Republic of China to the World Trade Organization (WTO) in 2001 marked not only the country's full integration into the international trade system but also its transformation into one of the key global hubs for foreign investment.

By joining the WTO, China created an open and stable market environment for foreign investors. As a result, the volume of foreign direct investment (FDI) increased severalfold within a relatively short period, significantly strengthening the country's industrial, infrastructural, and technological capacities [1]. This experience holds great relevance for many developing countries, including Uzbekistan, as examining China's approach, reforms, and investment policies offers valuable insights for nations on the path toward WTO accession.

This article analyzes the flow of foreign direct investment (FDI) in China before and after its accession to the World Trade Organization (WTO), examines the impact

of WTO membership on the investment climate, and proposes relevant lessons and alternative approaches for Uzbekistan.

Literature Review. China's accession to the World Trade Organization (WTO) in 2001 marked a significant milestone in its economic reform and global integration. Numerous studies have analyzed the implications of WTO membership on China's foreign direct investment (FDI) inflows. According to Lardy (2002) [2] and Bacchetta & Drabek (2004) [3], WTO membership compelled China to undertake substantial institutional and legal reforms, including greater transparency, stronger enforcement of intellectual property rights, and liberalization of previously restricted sectors. These reforms created a more predictable and secure investment environment, significantly enhancing investor confidence.

Research by Tang and Wei (2009) [4] found that WTO-related trade liberalization reduced tariffs and non-tariff barriers, thereby improving market access for foreign firms. This openness was particularly appealing to export-oriented FDI, as firms sought to use China as a manufacturing hub integrated into global supply chains.

Zhang (2005) [5] emphasizes that the impact of WTO accession was uneven across sectors. For instance, sectors previously restricted to joint ventures or state control - such as finance, telecommunications, and retail - saw a surge in FDI as they were gradually opened to foreign participation. Feng and Wang (2021) [6] support this, noting that post-WTO liberalization in services attracted higher-quality investment and technology spillovers.

Some scholars, such as Gallagher (2005) [7], caution that WTO accession alone did not guarantee increased FDI. They argue that investment decisions are also shaped by global economic conditions, labor costs, and existing industrial bases. Furthermore, the distinction between efficiency-seeking and market-seeking FDI is crucial in evaluating post-WTO trends.

Research Methodology. The study was grounded in a combination of inductive and deductive reasoning, along with methods of comparison and systematic analysis. To investigate the research questions, quantitative approaches were employed, focusing on the collection and examination of numerical data, with an emphasis on statistical analysis.

Analysis and Discussion of Results. The impact of foreign trade on investment refers to how international trade activities - such as exports and imports - affect the volume, direction, and efficiency of inward and outward investment flows within a country [8]. The key aspects that explain this relationship are illustrated below (Figure 1).

Market Expansion and Increased Investment Attractiveness. The expansion of export opportunities opens new markets for foreign investors. Countries with large markets attract more foreign investors, as the potential for selling products increases. For example, China's export-oriented policy has encouraged many international companies to invest in the country [8].

Fig. 1. The Impact of foreign trade on investment

Source: prepared by the author

Currency Earnings and Macroeconomic Stability. The currency reserves generated from exports improve the financial condition of a country. A stable currency policy reduces the level of risk for investors.

Resource Efficiency and the Competitive Environment. The import of advanced technologies and modern equipment increases production efficiency. This, in turn, helps in the effective utilization of existing investments and serves as an incentive for new investments. As foreign trade expands, competition with foreign companies intensifies, encouraging local businesses to invest in new technologies in order to remain competitive.

Capital Flows and Production Diversification. Trade liberalization increases the attractiveness of the market for foreign investors. They are more likely to invest in countries with a stable export-import balance. As opportunities to access export markets expand, producers are motivated to develop new products. This, in turn, requires directing investments towards new industries.

When foreign trade is properly managed, it plays a crucial role in attracting investments, bringing in technologies, enhancing export potential, and ensuring economic growth. However, this process also involves risks, which can be mitigated through effective trade policies, improving the investment climate, and ensuring economic stability [8].

Below, the impact of investments will be examined based on data from China before and after its accession to the WTO.

Pre-WTO Accession Period (1979-2001). The “Open Door Policy” initiated in China in 1978 marked a turning point in the country’s history. Based on this policy, the Chinese government began implementing market-oriented reforms in the

economy and focused on attracting foreign investments. Starting from 1979, foreign direct investments (FDI) were officially allowed in China, and the initial legal framework for this was established [9]. However, during this period, China was not fully integrated into the global trading system and did not fully align with international trade and investment norms.

According to statistical data from the World Bank, the volume of FDI flowing into China was only \$80,000 in 1979, but by 2000, this figure had reached \$42 billion (Figure 2). This growth was relatively slow but steady, supported by the economic zones established by the government, tax incentives, and inexpensive labor. Specifically, the free economic zones created in the mid-1980s (such as Shenzhen, Zhuhai, and other areas in southern China) became testing grounds for foreign investors.

Fig. 2. Foreign Direct Investment Flows to China from 1979 to 2000 (in million USD) [11]

Nevertheless, the lack of WTO membership, the instability of regulatory institutions, and the absence of guarantees for freedom of expression and property rights limited the flow of investments. International investors, in particular, were skeptical about the legal protection of their investments and contractual stability. However, the Chinese government carried out gradual reforms to address these issues and strengthen investor confidence.

Another important feature of this period was that China based its investment policy on export-oriented industrial sectors. Investments were primarily directed towards manufacturing, assembly, textiles, electronics, and light industries, as these sectors were competitive in international markets and considered profitable due to inexpensive labor. In conclusion, between 1979 and 2001, China laid an important foundation for attracting FDI. Although FDI during this period was relatively low, the country began implementing the necessary economic, institutional, and legal

reforms required for WTO accession. This, in turn, served as the basis for the subsequent sharp increase in investment flows

WTO Accession and Drastic Changes (2001-2023). China's accession to the World Trade Organization (WTO) on December 11, 2001, marked a significant turning point in the country's economic history. This membership not only represented full integration into the international trade system but also positioned China as an open, reliable, and stable market for global investors. Within the framework of WTO membership, China aligned its trade and investment systems with international standards, including the protection of intellectual property rights, the simplification of customs procedures, and the systematic regulation of subsidy and support policies.

Fig. 3. Foreign Direct Investment Flows to China from 2001 to 2023 (in million USD) [11]

In 2001, the volume of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) flowing into China amounted to \$47 billion. By 2021, this figure had surpassed \$344 billion (Figure 3). In other words, within 20 years, the volume of investments increased more than sevenfold. This growth rate reflects the country's reforms, global confidence, and China's central role in the global production chain.

Between 2001 and 2023, the highest volume of FDI was recorded in 2021—a period that, despite the COVID-19 pandemic, can be explained by China's stable economic policies and the growth of its production capacities [10].

At the same time, WTO membership also led to changes within China's domestic political and economic system: state-owned enterprises were reformed, the private sector was strengthened, and transparency in the business environment increased [11].

The lowest level of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in China was recorded in 1979, amounting to only \$80,000. This period marked the early stages of China's

opening-up policy, during which international investors had yet to develop confidence in the country [12]. In contrast, the highest level of FDI was observed in 2021, surpassing \$344 billion [13] (Figure 4).

This can be explained by China's transformation into a global manufacturing hub after its accession to the WTO, the deepening of reforms, and the strengthening of international trust.

Fig. 4. Foreign Direct Investment Flow to China from 1979 to 2023 (in million USD) [11]

Based on the graph above, it can be observed that FDI volume increased from \$80 thousand in 1979 to its highest level of \$344 billion in 2021. This indicates that the difference between the lowest and highest levels represents approximately a 4.3-million-fold growth over 40 years [14]. This growth is attributed to China's well-planned economic policy, integration with international organizations, and the favorable environment created for investors.

In conclusion, China's experience demonstrates that effective domestic reforms and active participation in the global economic system significantly enhance FDI flows.

China's accession to the WTO created vast opportunities for attracting FDI in various sectors, including high technology, automotive, logistics, finance, e-commerce, and others. At the same time, international corporations began to view China not only as a consumer market but also as a hub for manufacturing and R&D (research and development) activities.

However, a decline in FDI was observed between 2022 and 2023: in 2022, the figure was \$190 billion, and in 2023, it fell to only \$42.7 billion [15]. This decline can be attributed to the geopolitical situation, strategic competition between China and the United States, technological sanctions, and a relative decrease in investor

confidence. Additionally, the tightening of internal regulations in China and increasing pressure on the private sector have also influenced this trend.

Nevertheless, as a member of the WTO, China remains a leading player in global investment flows. By adhering to WTO regulations, it continues to protect its strategic sectors and develop industries based on advanced technologies.

Alternative Pathways and Lessons for Uzbekistan. Since gaining independence, Uzbekistan has placed significant emphasis on attracting foreign direct investment (FDI) to develop various sectors of its economy. Between 1992 and 2023, the volume of FDI has fluctuated annually, with these changes directly linked to the economic, political, and institutional reforms undertaken by the country.

Key Stages of Investment Flow: From the 5th chart below, it can be seen that starting from 1997, the volume of FDI began to grow steadily. During the 2004-2010 period, economic reforms and a focus on the energy and mining industries led to a significant increase in investments. For example, in 2010, the volume of investments amounted to \$1.66 billion [16].

Between 2011 and 2017, the volume of FDI remained stable, exceeding \$1.66 billion in 2016. However, in 2018, this figure sharply declined to around \$624 million. This situation indicates a temporary decrease in investor confidence [17].

2018–2023 (New Phas-Openness and Activity): Since 2018, investments have seen a sharp increase. Notably, in 2019, foreign direct investment reached \$2.31 billion; in 2021, it was \$2.28 billion; and in 2022, a record high of \$2.65 billion was recorded. This growth is attributed to the reforms implemented under the leadership of President Sh. Mirziyoyev, the adoption of an open economic policy, and the strengthening of legal guarantees [18].

Fig. 5. Direct Foreign Investments (FDI) Attracted to Uzbekistan between 1992 and 2023 (in million USD) [11]

Uzbekistan's recent foreign trade-oriented policies, its approach based on the principle of openness, and the ongoing reforms have significantly improved the investment climate. In the near future, it is possible to sustain this trend, further increase the volume of FDI by addressing problematic areas, and ensure economic stability.

China's experience of joining the WTO and the subsequent sharp increase in foreign direct investment (FDI) can serve as an important source of lessons and strategic approaches for Uzbekistan. Both countries, at their respective stages of development, require foreign investments, have limited domestic market sizes, and have pursued economic reforms. Therefore, adapting China's experience to the specific context of Uzbekistan is of considerable importance.

1. External Openness and Institutional Reforms

By joining the WTO, China strengthened its institutions, implemented reforms in line with international standards, and created a secure environment for investors. Uzbekistan must also accelerate institutional reforms aimed at attracting investment, including external openness, legal protection, property rights, and contract enforcement. WTO membership, or the establishment of a legal environment aligned with WTO standards, will enhance the confidence of international investors.

2. Identifying Strategic Sectors and Targeted Investment Policy

China implemented an investment policy focused on manufacturing sectors, effectively utilizing its production capacities and low-cost labor. Uzbekistan, on the other hand, can pursue a targeted investment policy focusing on sectors such as natural resources, energy, agriculture, textiles, IT, and logistics. This approach would enhance the effectiveness of FDI and stimulate economic growth.

3. Regional Integration and WTO-Oriented Actions

Uzbekistan is actively pursuing membership in the WTO. China's experience demonstrates that WTO membership not only provides trade privileges but also serves as a strong external impetus for reforms. Therefore, during Uzbekistan's accession process, it must align its internal policies and advance regional cooperation (such as with the Eurasian Economic Union and the Turkic Council) in accordance with WTO requirements.

4. Innovation Capacity and Localization

China, in the long term, not only attracted foreign investments but also achieved the localization of technologies, workforce development, and the establishment of its own industries. Similarly, Uzbekistan must assess investments not only in terms of quantity but also in terms of quality, prioritizing investment projects aimed at producing innovative products. This will ensure a transition to sustainable and high-tech economic growth.

The sharp increase in FDI flows following China's accession to the WTO can serve as a strong impetus and strategic roadmap for Uzbekistan. However, it is important not to directly replicate this path but rather to adapt it to Uzbekistan's specific conditions. If Uzbekistan aligns its WTO accession process with systematic reforms, legislation consistent with international standards, and a targeted investment policy, it will undoubtedly achieve positive results in attracting FDI.

Conclusion. In conclusion, China serves as an important analytical subject for Uzbekistan. The analysis shows that even before joining the WTO, China had implemented consistent reforms to attract FDI, however, it was through WTO membership that this process became systematic, legally grounded, and expedited. As a result, the country became an active participant in the global trading system, gained the confidence of international investors, and succeeded in transforming into a manufacturing and technological hub.

This experience is highly relevant for Uzbekistan: when attracting investments, it is not only external policies or incentive measures that matter, but also legal and institutional stability, legislation aligned with international standards, and an open and transparent economic environment, which serve as decisive factors. Furthermore, WTO membership can be seen as a crucial way for Uzbekistan to expand external trade opportunities, modernize production, and align the investment climate with global standards.

Thus, based on China's experience, Uzbekistan should view WTO membership not only as an external political objective but also as a catalyst for internal reforms. Its investment policy should be shaped by strategic planning, innovative approaches, and regional cooperation.

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